

Local Government in Spain

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Local Financial Arrangements

3.1. Local Financial Arrangements in Spain: An Introduction

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General Structure

The Spanish local finance dimension represents the 6 per cent of the Spanish GDP, smaller than the countries around us (11,1 per cent of EU GDP). In terms of national accounts, local government expenditure accounts for 13,7 per cent of the total public expenditure. Regarding tax revenue (excluding social security contributions), local taxes represent 16.4 per cent of the total tax revenue.⁴

Local government financing in Spain is an exclusive competence of the state with hardly any involvement from autonomous communities (regions). However, some regions have established additional funds other than those considered here, thereby transferring part of their own tax revenues to local governments. These funds are of little and unequal relevance in qualitative terms.

Public Revenues

Local government financing is mainly based on taxes (52,9 per cent of its revenues), higher than the European average (38,1 per cent);⁵ the latter trend lends greater fiscal autonomy. The general transfers from the state budget to the municipalities cover a small part of their current income (22,2 per cent in 2015).⁶ Since the economic crisis in 2008, the differential growth of local taxes (31 per cent) with respect to general transfers from the state (2,1 per cent) is strengthened. The majority of the general transfers are unconditional transfers, from the Supplementary Fund for Financing (*Fondo complementario de financiación* - FCF) for the large municipalities (more than 75,000 inhabitants and provincial and autonomous communities' capitals), and the Local Sharing of the state Revenues (*Participación municipal en los ingresos del Estado* - PIE) for the rest of the municipalities. One issue of the general transfers system is that the changes of population between municipalities are not reflected in the transfers from FCF. The latter does not occur in the case of transfers from PIE. The FCF is determined, for each budgetary year, taking into consideration the rise on state tax revenues between the system base year (2004) and the year concerned. The PIE is also based on the rise on state tax

⁴ Ministry of Finance, 'Recaudación y Estadísticas del Sistema Tributario Español 2006 – 2016' (2019) 100 and 107.

⁵ Ministry of Finance, 'Informe de la Comisión de Expertos para la Revisión del Modelo de Financiación Local' (2017).

⁶ See *ibid.*

revenues, but once the total participation has been determined, the latter is distributed between the municipalities essentially taking into account three variables: population, average tax effort and the inverse of fiscal capacity.⁷

Tax System

Spain shows high shares of total taxes received by the non-central authorities (one of the highest in the EU together with Sweden, Germany, Belgium and Denmark), close to the 10 per cent of the total taxes⁸. The local tax system is primarily based on actual taxes on property (in particular, Real Property Tax – *Impuesto sobre Bienes Inmuebles* – IBI) that, in some occasions, have little connection with the ability to pay of the concrete taxpayer. The taxes for the provision of services have a moderate position in the total amount of revenue collected.

Public Spending

The structure of the local expenditure is focused on the traditional municipal functions, having a lower relative weight regarding welfare state benefits (0.8 per cent of the GDP on social protection, health and education services, compared with 6.1 per cent in the EU). Since the entry into force of the current financing system in 2004 until 2015, the local public spending has increased by 31 per cent. The most significant items are: economy and commerce (112.2 per cent), population aging (88.4 per cent), general services (67.2 per cent), fire protection services (57.7 per cent), waste management (54 per cent), transport (42.9 per cent) and sports and leisure services (41.7 per cent), accounting for 46.1 per cent of total expenditures in 2015. The rise in public expenditure has been more pronounced in municipalities with less than 50,000 inhabitants. However, since the beginning of the crisis in 2008, the local public spending has decreased significantly (-7.7 per cent in terms of GDP), a substantial reduction exceeding those of EU countries (-1.8 per cent), while the income has grown at a faster rate (8.3 per cent). This decrease is mainly the result of a strict application of the national rules on budgetary discipline, such as the obligation of maintain a budgetary position close to balance or in surplus or the fulfillment of the expenditure benchmark (mandates set out in Article 135 of the Spanish Constitution and Articles 11(4) and 12, respectively, of Spanish Organic Law no 2/2012 on Budgetary Stability and Financial Sustainability).

⁷ See report section 3.2. on Financing Rural Local Governments Faced with Ageing and Dispersion.

⁸ European Commission, 'Taxation Trends in the European Union. Data for the EU Member States, Iceland and Norway' (2018).

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